

Efficacy of fungicides for control of rice tungro disease

G. Bhaktavatsalam, S.K. Mohanty, and S.K. Singh, Division of Plant Pathology, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

Tungro is considered an important disease of rice in Southeast Asia and in the southeastern states of India. Tungro virus disease can be managed through vector control (Bae and Pathak 1969, Shukla and Anjaneyulu 1980, Satapathy and Anjaneyulu 1984). Dubey (1980) reported that Bavistin, a fungicide, was effective in controlling leaf crinkle virus of urdbean. This prompted us to test fungicides for the therapeutic recovery of tungro on rice. We tested 12 fungicides (three granular, three EC formulations, and six wettable powders) under net-house conditions for therapeutic recovery of plants that were previously infected with tungro disease. One-month-old Jaya seedlings were planted in four rows of 10 seedlings per tray. Ten seedlings were healthy and 10 seedlings each of three replications were inoculated with three viruliferous hoppers per seedling in galvanized iron-mesh cages. The top of the cage was covered with muslin cloth and tightened with a rubber band. After symptoms were expressed (about 10–12 d after inoculation), each tray was sprayed with the fungicide at recommended doses at weekly intervals. Five such sprays were given. Virus quantification and symptomatology before the treatments showed a yellow color of the youngest leaf, which is a typical tungro symptom. After treatment with effective fungicides, the yellow color gradually fades away and the

plant is able to recover. Two trays were not sprayed with fungicide (each tray has 20 healthy seedlings and 20 inoculated seedlings) and these served as a control. The height of the plants and number of tillers were observed and plant yield determined.

The fungicides tested were Oryzomate, Coratop, Kitazin, Hinosan, Tilt, Validamycin, Fongorene, Chlorothanil, Rovral, Topsin, Dithane M-45, and Bavistin. Of these, Coratop and Oryzomate resulted in plant recovery to the extent of a 10% reduction in height, 11.6 average number of tillers, and 14.8 yield per plant in grams. The corresponding figures in the control (inoculated) were 70%, 2.2, and 0.9, respectively. Kitazin and Fongorene showed moderate re-

covery (see table). The statistical design used in this experiment was a complete randomized design. ANOVA was calculated and it was found that the critical difference value for percent reduction in height was 25.4, 3.3 for average number of tillers, and 4.2 for yield per plant, values that are significantly different from those observed in Oryzomate and Coratop. It was difficult to make a group comparison of fungicides, even though a significant difference exists between granular insecticides and EC formulations. Among the wettable powders, Fongorene, Topsin, Dithane, and M-45 were more effective than other fungicides. The reason for comparing Oryzomate and Coratop with the healthy control is to show how effective these

Evaluation of fungicides in terms of ability to control rice tungro disease.

Fungicide	Dose (1 g or 1 mL ai L ⁻¹)	% reduction in height compared with healthy plant	Tillers plant ⁻¹ (av no.)	Yield plant ⁻¹ (g)
Granular				
Oryzomate	1 g tray ⁻¹	10	11.6	14.8
Coratop	1 g tray ⁻¹	10	11.4	14.6
Kitazin	1 g tray ⁻¹	25	7.2	8.8
EC formulations				
Hinosan	1 mL L ⁻¹	60	3.1	1.8
Tilt	1 mL L ⁻¹	65	2.9	1.9
Validamycin	2 mL L ⁻¹	70	2.6	1.6
Wettable powders				
Fongorene	1 g L ⁻¹	25	7.8	8.2
Chlorothanil	1 g L ⁻¹	60	2.4	2.0
Rovral	1 g L ⁻¹	65	2.7	1.4
Topsin	1 g L ⁻¹	25	8.0	7.8
Dithane M-45	1 g L ⁻¹	25	7.4	8.6
Bavistin	1 g L ⁻¹	65	2.8	1.5
Control (healthy)	–	–	11.8	15.4
Control (diseased)	–	70	2.2	0.9
CD (5%)		25.4	3.3	4.2

treatments are. They were significantly different from the diseased control.

References

Bae SJ, Pathak MD. 1969. Common leafhopper plant populations and incidence of tungro virus in

diazinon-treated and untreated rice plots. *J. Econ. Entomol.* 62:772-775.
 Dubey GS. 1980. Bavistin for the control of leaf crinkle virus of urdbean. Paper presented at the International Symposium of the Phytopathological Society, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi.

Satapathy MK, Anjaneyulu A. 1984. Use of cypermethrin, a synthetic pyrethroid, in the control of rice tungro virus disease and its vector. *Trop. Pest Manage.* 30:170-178.
 Shukla VD, Anjaneyulu A. 1980. Evaluation of systemic insecticides for control of rice tungro. *Plant Dis.* 64:790-792.

Trapping the adult whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino with baits

T. Elaiya Bharathi, V. KR. Sathiyandam, and P.M.M. David, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Killikulam, Vellanad 628252, Tamil Nadu, India

The whorl maggot, *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino (Diptera: Ephydriidae), attacks rice seedlings at transplanting (Reissig et al 1986). As the larva feeds on the tissues of unopened leaves, white or transparent patches become evident near the edges when they unfold. Pinholes on leaves, which break from the wind, are other symptoms of attack. The damaged plants remain stunted with a few tillers. Ephydriids cause a 10–20% yield loss in rice (Foote 1995). The adults are active during the day, with limited migration, and they are highly attracted to fishmeal bait (Reissig et al 1986). However, the strong odor of decomposing fishmeal is not acceptable to all human beings. Since behavioral approaches are key elements in integrated pest management (Foster and Harris 1997), we evaluated the attractiveness of two selected food attractant admixtures involving banana, soybean hydrolysate, vinegar, and palm oil.

Two 5-d-long field experiments were conducted in two locations (AC and RI, Killikulam, and a nearby farmer's field in Tamil Nadu, India) in 2000-01 using irrigated lowland rice vari-

Relative efficacy of baits in luring adult *H. philippina* in two locations.

Attractant admixture (95:4:1)	Traps (no.)	Flies captured (no. trap ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)		Pooled mean ^c
		Location 1 ^a	Location 2 ^b	
Banana pulp + vinegar + palm oil	10	24.8 (4.9)	16.1 (4.0)	20.4 (4.4)
Soybean hydrolysate + vinegar + palm oil	10	19.9 (4.4)	9.0 (3.0)	14.5 (3.7)

^aSignificant difference ($P < 0.01$), Student's $t = 4.1$. ^bSignificant difference ($P < 0.01$), Student's $t = 2.6$. ^cSignificant difference ($P < 0.01$), Student's $t = 3.5$. Numbers in parentheses are $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$ transformed values.

ety ADT36 immediately after transplanting. On each 0.4-ha site, fly traps were set up 1 m above the ground. Two attractant admixtures—banana pulp/soybean hydrolysate + vinegar + palm oil (95:4:1), selected after a preliminary round of evaluation with a few others—were each placed in 10 traps that were arranged at 10-m spacing in a row. The two rows were 20 m apart. The baits were placed in Horlicks® bottle lids (6 cm diameter) at 20 g (banana pulp) or 20 mL (soybean hydrolysate) per trap. Palm oil was added to the baits to prevent them from drying because of the high temperature (33.0 ± 4.5 °C; $74.5 \pm 13.5\%$ relative humidity). Each day, the attractant admixtures were placed in the bait chamber of the trap at 0600 and the trapped flies were counted at 1800. The

fly-catch data were compared by a paired t-test after $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$ transformation.

The results indicated that banana pulp + vinegar + palm oil (20.4 flies trap⁻¹ d⁻¹) was 29% significantly ($P < 0.01$) more attractive to adult *H. philippina* than soybean hydrolysate + vinegar + palm oil (9.0–19.9 flies trap⁻¹ d⁻¹).

References

Foote BA. 1995. Biology of shore flies. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.* 40:417-442.
 Foster SP, Harris MO. 1997. Behavioural manipulation methods for insect pest management. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.* 42:123-146.
 Reissig WH, Heinrichs EA, Litsinger JA, Moody K, Fiedler L, Mew TW, Barrion AT. 1986. Illustrated guide to integrated pest management in rice in tropical Asia. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. 411 p.